

CHINA–PAKISTAN ECONOMIC CORRIDOR. A GAME CHANGER FOR THE REGION

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ABSTRACT: *It is well said that Pakistan and China friendship is deeper than oceans, sweeter than honey and higher than Himalayas. Pakistan china friendship have so long history, both countries works together from decades. So there is need to reshape and enhance this friendship, starting new projects and new trade agreements which are helpful for both countries and can improve both countries economic situation. China have infrastructure and machinery for betterment of infrastructure, china can built the road, the railway track and the bridges, on the other hand Pakistan have lot of natural resources, deep see, labor power and ability to connect china with road way. So, in this scenario both countries agreed on China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). The China Pakistan Economic Corridor is a big game changer that will influence the geo-strategic, geo-economic and geo-political dimensions of the Central Asia, the great Middle East Region and South Asia. It will ripple effect on all passing through Pakistan and Pakistan's economy. China and Pakistan both get benefits from bilateral trade through China Pakistan economic corridor.*

KEYWORDS: *CPEC, China-Pakistan, Development, Economy, Friendship.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The different countries have designed different national and international strategies for the enhancement of economic interest and creating friendly environment in international trade. It is well said that Pakistan and China friendship is deeper than oceans, Sweeter than honey and higher than Himalayas. China is the closest friend of Pakistan. Both countries have started different projects for economic development in different periods of time. China always helps Pakistan in energy crises, better transportation facilities, and construction of hospitals to build better economic environment in the country. This paper focuses on economic conditions in trade and transportation between China and Pakistan. Here, this research paper discuss Pakistan-China economic corridor for geographic economic development of both regions. Pakistan and China get mutual benefits from this corridor. Pakistan's Gwadar port and China's Kashgar city are connected through Silk Road (Karakoram Highway). This corridor has based on transportation of the region, focuses on energy crises in Pakistan, development of backward areas of Pakistan such as Baluchistan province, cooperation and joint steps for bilateral trade between China and Pakistan (Jehanzeb, 2007).

Gwadar was the part of Oman in 1958 but it was enclave sold to Pakistan in 1958. Pakistan built a port at Gwadar in 1964. But unfortunately Gwadar port was ignored for 4 decades. In 1977 Gwadar port was integrated within Baluchistan. Pakistan and China started 1st phase of Gwadar seaport in 2002 and that project was completed within two years. Gwadar seaport is located in western province of Baluchistan in Pakistan. In southwest, the Iran's border and in northwest the Afghanistan's border are situated. Gwadar bounded by the western end of Baluchistan coast, Gulf of Oman in the southwest and the Persian Gulf in the west. Gwadar seaport has 600 km coastal belt with bays and beaches. The distance from Gwadar to Karachi is just 460 km, 624 nautical km east of Strait of Hormuz and 120 km Iran border in west. Gwadar seaport has great importance for Pakistan economy. It helps in increasing road revenues through gives passes of other countries trade. Gwadar port is a big symbol of Pakistan China friendship (Chang, 2014).

Pakistan and China decided to connect south Pakistan to western China by a road and expenditures on this road construction are 18 billion US dollars approximately. It will be helpful in economic progress

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of both countries. China-Pakistan economic corridor will link Gwadar and Kashgar through 2700 Km road network and 1800 Km rail track including 200 tunnels. That is the shortest route for Chinese trade and other economic benefits. In this corridor there are other projects being started such as, Expansion of Karakoram Highway. A 125 Mile tunnel, A fiber optic cable connecting both countries China to Rawalpindi, A Motorway from Kashgar to Gwadar and Baluchistan and as well as A rail link also planned in this China Pakistan Economic Corridor. China has agreed to develop infrastructure projects on Gwadar with the investment of 900.05 Million US dollars and China has also agreed to invest 52 Billion US dollars on other different major projects in Pakistan in upcoming 5 years. Other areas of Pakistan will also be linked by Gwadar such like Punjgurh, Turbot and Shahdakot.

This China Pakistan corridor is not the first one in history. As we know in early 19th century, sea and land routes have been used to assist in the globalization process in opening of Asia. In 1869 Suez Canal opened to aid great empires of great powers. The canal made trade through the Sinai Peninsula which was not only faster but also economical. The Great Britain, that was Super Power of the time made great use of it, by transporting soldiers, goods to Bombay and other economic activities.

Pakistan is the 1st South Asian country in the region to sign agreement with China on currency swap, expands large Chinese investment and large free trade agreement in South Asia. Pakistan wants to get great opportunities on road construction, pipe line networks, increasing FDI and enhancing the exports of the country.

This study argues that political and social relationship between China and Pakistan will increase bilateral trade, economic development and opening new ways for both of these countries through Gwadar and Kashgar special economic zone. It is well said that Pakistan "Looks East" and China's "Go West". China Pakistan policies aim to develop infrastructure, trade, energy and transportation in this region.

The objective of this study is to explain the significance of Kashgar city and Gwadar seaport, economic impact of this corridor on China and Pakistan and the significant impact on Baluchistan region of Pakistan.

Pakistan – China | Economic Corridor

2. CHINA-PAKISTAN TRADE AND INVESTMENT RELATIONS

From the last 6 decades, Pakistan and China have strong defense, political and economic relationships. Pakistan celebrated 2011 as the year of China- Pakistan friendship. Due to globalization, cooperation among different countries is more important for the geo-strategic, geo-political and geo-economic cooperation (Khan, 2013). In globalization, most of the developed nations focused on economic integration and economic development through creating regional cooperation framework. Therefore, countries focus on free trade agreements and bilateral agreements through regional cooperation strategies. Pakistan and China also enhance the regional economic cooperation, bilateral trade for the sustainable development in their region (Fazal-ur-Rahman, 2010). The leadership of both countries always tries to upgrade the level of cooperation in political, social and economic manners. Different bilateral economic, private and public sector agreements have been signed between the leaderships of both countries. China has great contribution in upgrading the infrastructure of Pakistan by different projects, such as, the expansion of Karakoram Highway, coastal highway, Gwadar seaport and several other energy projects. China and Pakistan always try to enhance the trade and investment opportunities in the region (Mahmood, 2011).

In the last 15 years, there has been high level of visits carried out by the leadership of both countries. Each visit emphasized on economic cooperation. Four important visits of both countries leadership were held in years 2000, 2005, 2010 and 2014. Each visit focuses on expansion of economic relationship especially in trade, expansion of roads, energy crisis and other investment areas.

In the last year the level of bilateral trade has been increased from one billion US dollars to 4 billion US dollars, but on the other side the growth of Pakistan's exports was decreased.

Pakistan and China Trade Pattern 2005-2010

Years	2005-06	2006-07	2007-08	2008-09	2009-10	
Exports	Value (000 \$)	354,092	575,903	684,793	701,043	1,153,861
	% Growth	31.02	24.14	18.91	2.37	64.59
Imports	Value (000 \$)	1,842,775	3,533,794	4,688,239	4,086,736	4,410,553
	% Growth	46.84	30.59	32.67	-12.83	7.92
Balance	Value (000 \$)	(1,488,683)	(2,957,891)	(4,003,446)	(3,385,693)	(3,260,716)
	% Growth	50.61	31.93	35.35	-15.43	-3.81
Export as % of Import	17.14	16.30	14.61	17.15	26.14	
Ratio of Import / export	5.83	6.14	6.85	5.83	3.83	

During the visit of Chinese minister to Pakistan in 2011, different areas of cooperation were identified, such as tourism, infrastructure, information technology, cooperation in agriculture sector and emphasizes on achieving the mutual economic benefits. During the visit, a MoU was signed between both countries. According to MoU, both countries agreed to cooperate in tourism, technical support, lease of Saindak gold and copper project, locomotive supply, pipeline of white oil. Construction of coastal highway and Gwadar port are also included in the agreement. MoU was also signed between PTCL and ZTE. China has also committed with Pakistan for the investment of 1 billion US dollars and China is also agreed in providing full technical support on these projects.

In November 2003, President Pervaiz Musharaf and in December 2004 Prime Minister Shoukat Aziz both visited China signed very important document that was known as "Joint Declaration on Direction of Bilateral Relations". In fact the documents were blueprinted for future cooperation between Pakistan and China. These documents emphasis on economic development relationships. In several other visits the leadership of both countries emphasis on expanding bilateral trade agreement, Chinese investment in Pakistan and Pakistan gives the status of "Free Market Economy" to China.

In 2005 China Pakistan trade showed increasing trend. In 2000 that trade was 1 billion dollars, in 2005 that 1 billion increased to 4.5 billion US dollars. Pakistan has the need of more investment in industrial sector that would help to increase the export of Pakistan and fill trade deficit.

During 2000-2005 Pakistan FDI increase 600% but the Chinese share was very low. In 2005 Chinese Prime Minister Wen Jiabao paid an official visit of Pakistan to attend the Pakistan China Business conference. He also delivered a speech on trade and economic cooperation between both countries.

He gave three suggestions for enhancing the scope of investment and bilateral trade.

1. Pakistan has large amount of natural resources. China will provide applicable technologies for the optimize use of these natural resources. In this way Pakistan China trade structure will improve. China will try to encourage investors to invest in Pakistan, for the sake of win-win results and create more opportunities of employment in Pakistan,
2. Both countries will focus on expanding business cooperation opportunities. The governments of both countries will promote the communication mechanism.
3. The cooperation on communication, information technology, science and finance should be increased in broader meaning of cooperation.

In 2008 Prime Minister Yousaf Raza Gilani attended the meeting of Asia Europe Summit (ASEM) in Beijing. During the visit Prime Minister addressed to Chinese cooperate leaders and invited them to explore potential investment areas in Pakistan. The Prime Minister also had bilateral trade meeting with heads of Chinese government.

In 2009 President Asif Ali Zardari visited China. The main purpose of this visit was to enhance the bilateral trade and focused on cooperation in agriculture sector; bring Chinese investment in Pakistan and economic cooperation among both countries. In the same year, President of Pakistan again visited China and signed MoU agreement. Cooperation in Fisheries sector was highlighted in this visit. That visit enhanced the cooperation in energy sector, building irrigation system including construction of small and large size dams.

During 2014 Prime Minister of Pakistan Nawaz Sharif visited China and met with new Chinese leadership. The great outcome of that visit was that an agreement on constructing roads was signed. That road will link Gwadar and Kashgar. This agreement is known as Kashgar Gwadar Economic Corridor (KGEC). It is absolutely big "Game Changer" for China and Pakistan. This agreement also includes Oil pipeline from Gwadar to Xinjiang and 200 tunnel railway track ("Sharif inaugurates China-Pakistan Economic Corridor project," 2014).

3. BENEFICIAL AND NECESSARY FOR PAKISTAN

Pakistan China Economic Corridor can play more significant role and can become a blessing for the economic development of Pakistan when FDI has sharply fallen. Poverty has increased to 41 % whereas economic losses due to "War on Terror" are as higher as 35 US billion dollars and industrial sector is operating at 50 % of its total potential due to short fall of energy crises. So that Economic Corridor will play an important role in the revival of Pakistan's economy because it is situated at the crossroad of huge supplying market. There are some reasons behind Chinese interest in building the Gwadar Kashgar road, one of them is China's being near to Central Asian countries through Pakistan. So China has interest for this Corridor to make a special economic zone. Strategic partnership between the two countries is also an important reason. China has also interest in proposed oil & gas pipeline from Gwadar and Iran to Kashgar across Pakistan. It will also generate transit and employment in Pakistan (Mahmood, 2011).

Pakistan wants to increase its trade and develop Baluchistan province. 1800 km railway line between Kashgar and Gwadar has proposed by both countries that would be a milestone in increasing not only bilateral trade but also integrate the regions of central Asia and south Asia economically. Though, earlier Gwadar port will serve only Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan and Tajikistan via Afghanistan due to geographical proximity (Ahmad, 2013). But now China-Pakistan economic corridor connected Gwadar by a land route through Kashgar. The Gwadar port will also serve Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan

(Asghar, 2014).

The master plan of this project shows that Gwadar port can capture up to 25 % of the national imports and export market by 2020, 15 percent of Pakistan's share of transit trade with cars, 40 % for Afghanistan and 12 % for Xinjiang. Regional inter-dependencies will also develop which in turn would create direct stakes in each other's stability and making economic partners of geographical neighbors.

Pakistan's major economy depends on sea-borne trade as it contributes 40 % to national GDP currency in 2004. Almost 10 year back, Pakistan's sea borne trade contribution was 36.3 % to the national GDP. More-than 90 % percent of international trade has also been transported through the sea. So China-Pakistan Economic Corridor connection to the surrounding areas through the development of rails and roads can gives fruitful results. Because through this connection trade from and to china and central Asia would prefer to adopt shortest route. As a result Gwadar Kashgar multiplying the trade benefits for Pakistan. Thus, port would produce various employment opportunities for people. It will also generate billions of dollars in transit revenues to get maximum benefits from maritime economics Pakistan needs to develop its shipping industry. But this would imply that a stable and secured environment is in place (Asghar, 2014).

Pakistan – China | Economic Corridor ▶

US\$ **20** BILLION

Worth Development Projects

- 1** Highway
Gwadar - Kunjrab
- 2** Motorway
Karachi - Lahore
- 3** Expressway
Muzaffarabad - Mirpur
- 4** Freight Trains
Gwadar - Kunjrab

Pakistan – China | Economic Corridor

1 Highway Gwadar – Khujerab

Length (Approx)	2,395 Km
Terrain	Mountainous, Rolling, Flat
Lanes	2-6
Lane width	3.65 m
Shoulder width	2 – 3 m (outer) 1 – 2 m (Inner)
Design Speed	70 – 120 Kph
Bridges, Tunnels and Avalanche Galleries	2 - 4 lanes
Estimated Cost	Rs. 1,200 Billion

Pakistan – China | Economic Corridor

2 Motorway Karachi – Lahore

Length (Approx)	1,186 Km
Terrain	Flat, Mountainous, Rolling
Lanes	6
Lane width	3.65 m
Shoulder width	3 m (outer) 1m (Inner)
Design Speed	120 Kph
Tunnel	To be determined after feasibility study
Bridges (Tentative)	6 Lanes over Indus, Ravi and Sutlej
Estimated Cost	Rs. 677 Billion

Pakistan – China | Economic Corridor ▶

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4. BENEFICIAL FOR BALUCHISTAN PROVINCE

Baluchistan though the poorest province of Pakistan, it has very low population but despite these facts it makes approximately 43% of the total area of country. Baluchistan is the major supplier of natural gas after Sindh. It has also rich mineral resources. At the point of RikoDiq in the Chaghi district of Baluchistan, the world's biggest coppers have been found here. So Baluchistan is also big supplier of copper and it is believed that these resources are even greater than those at Sarchesmesh in Iran and Escondido in Chile which are the second and third largest proven deposits of copper in the world. Indeed, as one analyst notes, if it were not for the strategic location of Baluchistan and the rich potential of oils uranium and other resources. It would be difficult to anyone fighting over this bleak, desolate and for bidding land (Khetran, 2011).

Due to the geo-strategic location of its Southwestern province Baluchistan, Pakistan has great and strong geo-political importance in the region. Southwestern province of Baluchistan is located at the cross road of South Asia, central Asia and the Middle East. That is why it has beneficial importance for Pakistan. Because it shares a 540 mile long border with Iran, in the west and a 723 mile long border with Afghanistan in the northwest, whereas through Indus valley, it also touch as the boundaries of the east and connects the Arabian Sea to the south regions which surround it are rich in oil and gas revenues like Afghanistan, Iran and the Persian Gulf they all are rich in these two natural resources (Ahmad, 2013). Whereas on the hand it is located in the midst of natural resources, the Strait of Hormuz which to an important route for global oil supplies, Baluchistan coast lies opposite to it, therefore it has possible resources to develop and become a center of international trade. In order to improve the economic development of Baluchistan, Gwadar Kashgar project is going to make its connection to national highway. This in turn will bring peace, harmony and stability of this backward province it will give good results. All natural resources of Baluchistan like precious metals minerals oil and gas could not be utilize properly due to lack of machinery, infrastructure and political will. To get benefit from all these natural resources there is need to pay attention on the development of infrastructure keeping expected economic activities from China Pakistan Economic Corridor in view. Because that project has potential to generate necessary resources for developing the require infrastructure for its operation (Khetran, 2011).

5. BENEFICIAL AND NECESSARY FOR CHINA

It has seemed now that Gwadar and Kashgar fall under Chines "Go West" and Pakistan's "Look East" policy. The most important part of Pakistan policy is its establishment of mutually beneficial relationship with China. Whereas China's main aim is to develop its relatively backward western region in particular Xinjiang which is restive as a consequences. The policy of "Look West" serves a dual purpose for China through economic development. It brings peace and stability and the use of this province for the purpose to gets more energy and trade transaction with rich central Asia.

In 2010 according to a report by the Paris based international energy agency China has become the largest energy consumer in the world better than USA. It plans to develop wide range of product and increase it energy supply to make easier supply to Persian Gulf and African oil to Western China, China has planned to build and oil refinery at Gwadar and Oil Pipeline from Gwadar to Xinjiang. This plan will reduce the distance by several thousand's miles the total length of the length of the suggested plan of gas pipeline from Gwadar port to Xinjiang to Eastern ports of Shanghai and Beijing through inland China 4500 Km. There is the distance of 10,000 Km from Shanghai port to Gwadar and Pakistan Gulf through the place of Indian ocean. This trade and energy transport from Persian Gulf and East-African states via Gwadar through Pakistan will reduce the distance of 1500 kilometer to a distance of just 2500

kilometer. so it is safe and secure to the maritime route. For reaching to the gulf Chinese oil tankers take 20 days. These oil tankers would reach to Gwadar, right to the mouth of the gulf, within 48 hours after the completion of the high-speed rail and road network across Pakistan. so Gwadar port secures for Chinese oil imports a safe and short route. Besides this Gwadar port has helped China to extend its presence in Arabian Sea and Persian Gulf from where China imports 60 percent of its energy.

To achieve economic, energy and commercial gains The Persian Gulf and the Arabian Sea remain an open area where regional and extra-regional states have always been committed. This would naturally result in a win-win situation for china and Pakistan for two regions. Firstly china and Pakistan are directly connected through the land route while India and Pakistan are not directly connected to each other. Secondly, Cha Bahar is close to the Strait of Hormuz and forced by its shallow water. Without chine cooperation Pakistan cannot compete India. India's growing interest in Arabian Sea worries both Pakistan and China with regard of economic interest in the region. India and Pakistan can't by pass each other in their excess to Afghanistan and central Asia. To utilize the full potential of Gwadar port for trade Pakistan need to stable Baluchistan. So that Pakistan can get accesses to the whole region including China, central Asia, Afghanistan, East Africa and middle East.

The Global Trade Of China – Shipping Route ▶

EXISTING Europe – Western China (19132 miles)

DISTANCE Middle East – Western China (12537 miles)

LONG DISTANCE & HIGH COST

The Global Trade Of China – Shipping Route

DISTANCE Europe – Western China (9535 miles)
SAVED Middle East – Western China (10242 miles)

**PAKISTAN - CHINA
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SHORT DISTANCE & LOW COST

6. CONCLUSION

Kashgar and Gwadar road will serve the underdeveloped regions of both countries. Rail and road link will improve the economies of both countries through trade and passing. That would have great importance for Baluchistan and Kyber Pakhtun Kha because that region is not linked with rail track.

Due to Kashgar Gwadar agreements both countries will achieve same goals in a democratic and cooperative manner and this road and rail agreement highlight the brotherhood relationship between China and Pakistan Governments. Kashgar Gwadar project also agreed on building of ports and pipelines with Kashgar Gwadar infrastructure.

In the South Asian region Pakistan serve as most beneficial ally for China. Pakistan has great geographic location that helps in connecting Central Asia and Middle East and South Asia. China has great trade share in international trade, so China wants safe passage through Kashgar and Gwadar Road and improve its status in international trade. Kashgar and Gwadar road will play an important role in regional integration of "South Asia" which includes Afghanistan, Iran and China. Pakistan is the 1st South Asian country to sign a currency swap and free trade agreement with Chines government and helps in providing big destination for Chines investment. China has fourth largest export market in Pakistan and Pakistan is second trading partner of China. In future Pakistan will get large benefits from Kashgar and Gwadar agreement which will help in boosting Pakistan's economy and that project must help in enhancing regional power for Pakistan. Kashgar Gwadar project will help in trade. China Pakistan trade will cross 15 Billion US dollars by 2015 due to that project.

THE FUTURE OF ECONOMIC CORRIDOR

A WIN-WIN SYNERGY FOR PAKISTAN & CHINA

Pak-China Trade will cross
US\$ 15 Billion by **2015**

Source: State Bank of Pakistan – Trade Statistics

7. REFERENCES

- Jehanzeb. (2007). The Trade Potential and Industrial Development in Gwadar. *Journal of Management Sciences*, 1(1), 88–101.
- Sharif inaugurates China-Pakistan Economic Corridor project. (2014). Retrieved from The Hindu website: <http://www.thehindu.com/todays-paper/tp-international/sharif-inaugurates-chinapakistan-economic-corridor-project/article6649863.ece>

- Asghar, S. (2014). Pak-China economic corridor: "A Fate Changer for Pakistan." Retrieved from Daily Times website: <http://www.dailytimes.com.pk/business/03-Dec-2014/pak-china-economic-corridor-a-fate-changer-for-pakistan>
- Khetran, M. S. B. (2011). Crisis in Balochistan. *Strategic Studies*, 31(1/2), 24–39.
- Mahmood, K. (2011). Pakistan-China strategic relations. *Strategic Studies*, 31(1/2), 9–15.
- Fazal-ur-Rahman, M. (2010). Pakistan-China trade and investment relations. *Strategic Studies*, 30(3/4), 100–108.
- Chang, G. G. (2014). China's big plans for Pakistan. *The National Interest*, 10.
- Ahmad, I. (2013). Pakistan's 'Regional Pivot' and the Endgame in Afghanistan. *IPRI Journal*, 13(2), 1–20.
- Khan, S. A. (2013). Geo-economic imperatives of Gwadar Sea Port and Kashgar economic zone for Pakistan and China. *IPRI Journal*, 13(2), 87–100.